

Selective Adsorption and its Significance. Part I. Nature of Selective Adsorption.

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A number of workers have determined selective adsorption on porous substances from binary mixtures (Williams, *Medd. K. Vetenskapsakad. Nobel-Inst.*, 1913, 2, No. 23; Ostwald and Izaguirre, *Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 30, 279; Patrick and Jones, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1; Bartell and Scheffler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2507; Jones and Outridge, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1574; B. S. Rao, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 615). The selective adsorption may be expressed as

$$S = \frac{m}{g} (C_1 - C_2) \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where S denotes selectivity; m , wt. of the liquid mixture used; g , wt. of the silica gel in equilibrium with the liquid mixture; C_1 , the initial conc. of the selectively adsorbed component expressed in wt. fraction; and C_2 , the equilibrium conc. of the selectively adsorbed component expressed in wt. fraction.

Williams (*loc. cit.*) uses a similar formula but calls S , the "Apparent adsorption". Bartell and Scheffler (*loc. cit.*) employ a similar formula but express C_1 and C_2 in mole fractions. S is then termed "Molar selectivity". All these equations give the same type of curve when S is plotted against the equilibrium concentration, C_2 . In this paper an attempt is made to explain the values of selectivity obtained with two samples of silica gel.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Gels used.—Two types of silica gel A, and B were prepared. Gel A was prepared by Patrick's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 951). In the case of the gel B, the precipitate of silicic acid, which appeared during the addition of the sodium silicate solution to hydrochloric acid did not disappear completely. The jellies that were so obtained were washed with distilled water, till the washed liquid gave no test for chloride. The washed jellies were dried by passing warm air and finally activated in a current of dry air at 360° for 5 hours. Gel A had the usual *glassy* appearance while gel B was *opaque*. The water

content of the gels was determined by igniting the samples in a platinum crucible at blast lamp temperature; the gel A yielded 3.35% of water while B gave 3.64%.

Benzene, carbon tetrachloride and heptane :—The C. P. liquids were dried over phosphorus pentoxide and distilled.

Absolute alcohol was dried over aluminium amalgam and distilled. Pyridine was dried over caustic potash and distilled. All these liquids showed no change of refractive index when treated with the activated gel.

Selective adsorption at 30° was determined by the method described by B. S. Rao (*loc. cit.*). The following mixtures were used: (1) Alcohol—benzene, (2) Alcohol—carbon tetrachloride, (3) Benzene—heptane, and (4) Pyridine—heptane. The composition of the equilibrium mixtures was determined by means of a Pulfrich refractometer. The results are given below. In the tables C_2 represents the equilibrium concentration of the selectively adsorbed liquid; S , the selectivity as calculated from equation (i) and $\psi = \frac{S}{1-C_2}$ whose significance is described later.

TABLE I.

Benzene—alcohol.

Alcohol as the selectively adsorbed liquid

Gel A.			Gel B.		
$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 1000.$	$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 100.$
0.2	6.3	6.3	0.4	10.3	10.3
0.4	12.8	12.8	1.2	15.2	15.3
2.6	19.0	19.5	2.8	18.9	19.4
6.1	20.4	22.2	8.6	20.5	22.4
11.0	20.2	22.7	13.8	19.1	22.2
18.4	18.0	23.1	20.3	17.6	22.2
42.6	12.1	21.9	43.8	11.1	19.6
68.6	5.36	17.1	69.0	5.2	19.2
81.6	2.4	14.7	84.4	2.7	17.0
94.1	0.3	5.5			

TABLE II.

Alcohol—carbon tetrachloride.

Alcohol as the selectively adsorbed liquid.

$C_2 \times 100.$	Gel A.		$C_2 \times 100.$	Gel B.	
	$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 100.$		$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 100.$
0.2	18.4	18.5	1.7	20.5	20.9
4.8	22.9	24.0	7.0	21.2	23.8
9.2	22.7	24.3	11.0	20.6	23.2
20.6	18.1	22.8	23.0	16.7	21.7
41.8	12.6	21.6	44.0	11.3	20.1
67.8	8.5	17.2	68.8	4.7	15.1
86.8	1.5	11.4	87.6	1.0	7.7
95.2	0.5	10.0	95.2	0.3	6.3

TABLE III

Benzene—heptane.

Benzene as the selectively adsorbed liquid.

$C_2 \times 100.$	Gel A.		$C_2 \times 100.$	Gel B.	
	$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 100.$		$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 100.$
2.0	4.3	4.4	2.2	3.9	3.9
4.8	6.6	6.8	8.2	8.4	9.12
7.0	7.8	8.4	12.0	10.1	11.5
10.6	9.7	10.9	21.0	12.1	15.3
41.8	11.5	19.8	44.0	11.1	19.8
64.4	7.6	21.4	67.0	7.2	21.8
80.4	4.6	22.9	94.6	0.8	14.8
94.3	1.1	18.6			

TABLE IV.

Pyridine-heptane.

Pyridine as the selectively adsorbed liquid.					
Gel A.			Gel B.		
$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 100.$	$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$	$\psi \times 100.$
0.1	11.8	11.8	0.2	14.6	14.6
4.3	26.3	27.4	5.9	26.6	28.3
7.0	27.5	37.2	15.1	27.4	32.3
16.7	29.2	35.1	23.2	26.8	34.9
33.6	25.6	38.5	37.1	23.3	37.0
49.0	19.5	38.1	51.2	17.3	35.4
60.0	15.3	38.2	61.0	13.8	35.3
76.5	8.6	36.6	79.7	6.7	32.9
88.0	4.1	34.6	89.1	3.62	33.6

The results obtained have been indicated graphically in Figs. 1-4. It will be noticed that the alcohol is preferentially adsorbed (Figs. 3 and 4) over the entire range from its binary mixtures with benzene and carbon tetrachloride. Pyridine and benzene (Fig. 1) are preferentially adsorbed from their binary mixtures with heptane. In general, gel A exhibited higher selectivity than gel B. In benzene—heptane mixtures, however, (Fig. 1) the two selectivity curves were almost identical (this has been explained later). The adsorption of pyridine from the heptane mixtures, however, (Fig. 1) is of particular interest since it displays the highest selectivity of all the mixtures tried hitherto.

DISCUSSION.

The results obtained may be explained on the assumption that the adsorption of the liquids on silica gel is of two kinds, *viz.* (a) The adsorption on the surface of the gel, and (b) the capillary condensation. Jones and Outridge (*loc. cit.*) have suggested that the liquid held in the capillaries is identical in composition with the bulk liquid. The selectivity phenomenon noticed, seems, therefore, to be entirely due to the adsorption on the surface.

With Langmuir we can assume that the adsorption at the gel surface, is unimolecular; in other words the influence of the surface forces will be confined only to molecules adjacent to the walls of the solid. In the case of selective adsorption with alcohol-benzene mixtures, although both the liquids are adsorbed on the gel surface, the amount of alcohol present at the surface will be greater than the amount of benzene. This may be due to the greater attraction of the silica surface for the more polar liquid.

A relationship can be deduced between selectivity and the amount of alcohol held at the silica surface. Let 1 g. of the gel adsorb m' g. of the liquid mixture at the equilibrium concentration C_2 . Suppose a portion m_1 of this mixture is held at the surface while the remainder $(m' - m_1)$ is condensed in the capillaries. Let C_u be the concentration of alcohol in m_1 and C_g in m' the total liquid adsorbed. Then the total alcohol adsorbed per g. of the gel

$$= m' C_g = m_1 C_u + (m' - m_1) C_2$$

Hence
$$m' (C_g - C_2) = m_1 (C_u - C_2)$$

It has been shown (effect of temperature on selective adsorption, Eq. ii) that

$$S = m' (C_g - C_2) \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Therefore,
$$S = m' (C_g - C_2) = (C_u - C_2) m_1 \dots (iii)$$

Thus selectivity represents the excess of alcohol present at the surface of 1 g. of the gel (owing to the selective nature of adsorption) over what would have been present if the bulk concentration had continued right up to the surface.

Suppose the excess of alcohol ψ is removed from m_1 , then the remaining mixture $(m_1 - \psi)$ will have a concentration C_2

i.e.,
$$m_1 C_u = \psi + (m_1 - \psi) C_2$$

or
$$\psi (1 - C_2) = m_1 (C_u - C_2) = S \text{ (by Eq. iii)} \dots (iv)$$

or
$$\psi = \frac{S}{1 - C_2} \dots \dots \dots (v)$$

Thus ψ the excess of alcohol at the surface can be calculated from known values of S and C_2 . A similar equation has been derived by Williams (*loc. cit.*) for U_0 , the "apparent adsorption".

$$U_0 = M (C_0 - C) / G(100 - C) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

where M denotes wt. of the binary mixture; G , wt. of the gel in equilibrium mixture; C_0 , the initial conc. of the solute expressed in % by wt; and C , the equilib. conc. of the solute in % by wt.

If the concentration, C is expressed in weight fraction, this equation will be identical with the one that is obtained for ψ . But instead of representing ψ as the excess of alcohol taken by the surface, Williams considers U_0 as the true adsorption of the solute when no solvent is adsorbed but in practice both the liquids of the binary mixture are adsorbed. Hence the interpretation of ψ as the excess of alcohol taken up by the gel gives a better picture of the phenomenon.

The true adsorption (the total weight of alcohol taken up by the gel from the mixture) can be easily calculated by the selectivity data. Williams (*loc. cit.*) has calculated the true adsorption of alcohol on the gel by making use of the two equations

$$U = U_0 + WC / 100 - C \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (vii)$$

and $I = W + U \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (viii)$

where U = wt. of the solute adsorbed when the equilib. conc. is C ; W , wt. of the solvent in the same condition; I , total wt. of the solute and the solvent. I is determined experimentally by finding out the weight of the mixture adsorbed in the vapour phase at the equilibrium concentration. Jones and Outridge (*loc. cit.*) assumed that the internal gel volume is constant and calculated I for n -butyl alcohol and benzene mixtures by the equation

$$I = V D \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (ix)$$

where V denotes the internal gel volume, and D , the density of the solution within the gel.

Assuming that the density-concentration curve of n -butyl alcohol and benzene is almost a straight line, D is calculated by a method of successive approximation. The authors determined V by experiment and noticed a slight variation of V with different liquids. This they attributed to the experimental error. The validity of this assumption has been more vigorously studied by the present author (compare, p. 331). It is found that in the case of mixtures, only about a

certain concentration, the volume of the liquid taken up by the gel will be that of the preferentially adsorbed liquid.

The true adsorption can be calculated from the selectivity data in a simpler manner. Let Q be the weight of alcohol taken up by the gel when in equilibrium with the saturated vapour of alcohol, then the total internal gel volume for alcohol

$$= \frac{Q}{D_A} \text{ where } D_A \text{ is the density of alcohol.}$$

The volume of the adsorbed liquid having concentration C_2

$$= \frac{Q - \psi}{D_A} = m' - \psi$$

where m' is total amount of the liquid adsorbed (*cf.* Eq. ii). The true adsorption of alcohol (*i.e.*, the total amount in m')

$$= C_2(m' - \psi) + \psi = C_2(Q - \psi) \frac{D'}{D_A} + \psi \quad \dots \quad (x)$$

where D' is the density of the mixture at a concentration C_2 . Similarly "True adsorption" U of benzene

$$= (1 - C_2)(Q - \psi) \frac{D'}{D_A} \quad \dots \quad (xi)$$

The above method of calculating the true adsorption is simpler than that employed by Jones and Outridge, (*loc. cit.*) as it does not involve the calculation of D (density of the adsorbed liquid) by the method of successive approximations.

It is of interest to note that in binary mixtures of *n*-butyl alcohol and benzene investigated by Jones and Outridge (*loc. cit.*, p. 1580, Table II) the apparent adsorption x/m is equal in magnitude to the true adsorption U . This follows from the fact that the true adsorption

$$= C_2(Q - \psi) \frac{D'}{D_A} + \psi = C_2\psi \frac{D'}{D_A} + \psi(1 - C_2 \frac{D'}{D_A}) \quad \dots \quad (xii)$$

At low concentrations, C_2 is very small in comparison with ψ so that the factors containing C_2 may be neglected. Hence the true adsorption

$$= \psi = \frac{S}{1 - C_2} = S_s$$

Thus Jones and Outridge get U almost equal to S till C_2 reaches a value of 2%.

FIG. 1.

1 and 2 for benzene-heptane and pyridine-heptane mixtures with gel A ; 3 for that of latter mixture with gel B.

FIG. 2.

1-3 for ψ - C_2 curves for gel A, gel B and gel A+B respectively in pyridine-heptane mixture.

FIG. 3.
Benzene-alcohol.

1, 2 represent S - C_2 curves for gel B and A respectively.
3, 4 represent ψ - C_2 curves for gel B and A respectively.

FIG. 4.
Alcohol- CCl_4

1, 2 represent S - C_2 curves for gel A and B respectively.
3, 4 represent S - ψ curves for gel B and A respectively.

In Tables I to IV, the values of ψ are given for different mixtures. When these are plotted (Figs. 1-4) it is seen that in the case of pyridine-heptane, the curve is almost horizontal between 30 and 70%

concentration of pyridine. The slope of $\psi - C_2$ curves increases in benzene-alcohol mixtures (Fig. 3) and is greatest in the benzene-heptane mixtures (Fig. 2). The horizontal portion of $\psi - C_2$ curve in the case of pyridine-heptane mixtures is of particular interest. If from the horizontal portion of the curve, ψ values at concentrations C'_2 and C''_2 are taken, we have

$$\psi = \frac{S'}{1 - C'_2} = \frac{S''}{1 - C''_2}$$

where S' and S'' are the selectivity values at C'_2 and C''_2 , respectively. Substituting for S in equation (iii) we get

$$\frac{m'_1(C'_u - C'_2)}{1 - C'_2} = \frac{m''_1(C''_u - C''_2)}{1 - C''_2}$$

where m'_1 and m''_1 are the weights of the mixtures on the gel surface at C'_2 and C''_2 ; C'_u , C''_u are the concentrations of alcohol at the surface for the equilibrium concentrations C'_2 and C''_2 . The difference in the value between m'_1 and m''_1 is negligible.

$$\text{So} \quad \frac{C'_u - C'_2}{1 - C'_2} = \frac{C''_u - C''_2}{1 - C''_2} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (xiii)$$

This relationship can only be satisfied if the values of C'_u and C''_u are very nearly to unity. In other words, the horizontal curve is obtained when the unimolecular layer at the gel surface consists of almost entirely of the selectively adsorbed component. If the value of C_u decreases, the slope of the $\psi - C_2$ curve increases. Thus the slope of the $\psi - C_2$ curves obtained with the two mixtures pyridine-heptane and benzene-heptane gives us an idea of the relative richness of the surface layer in the selectively absorbed component.

The anomalous behaviour of the two gels in the case of benzene-heptane mixtures can be satisfactorily explained. It has been shown by the author that silica gel adsorbs per g. of the gel a larger volume of pyridine (and other liquids like water and alcohol) than of liquids like benzene and heptane. The latter two are adsorbed in equal quantities at the surface of both the gels. Hence there is no appreciable difference in the selectivity values for the two gels with benzene-heptane mixtures. In the case of pyridine-heptane mixtures, different quantities of pyridine are adsorbed at the surfaces

of the two gels. Therefore a difference is noticed in the selectivity values for the two gels. In other words the two gels present the same amount of surface for benzene in the case of benzene-heptane mixtures, but different amounts of surface for pyridine in the case of pyridine-heptane mixtures.

Selectivity measurements can be employed for the comparison of the specific surfaces of different varieties of silica gel. Let S_a and S_b be the selectivity values of two types of silica gel at the same equilibrium concentration C_2 in an alcohol-benzene mixture. It has been shown by the author (Eq. iii) that $S = m_1(C_u - C_2)$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad \frac{S_a}{S_b} = \frac{m_a(C_{ua} - C_2)}{m_b(C_{ub} - C_2)}$$

where m_a and m_b and the wt. of the mixture taken by 1 g. each of gel A and gel B at the surface respectively ; C_{ua} and C_{ub} , the concentrations of alcohol (wt. fraction) at the surface of the gel A and gel B. The difference in adsorptive capacity of the two gels is to be attributed to the difference in silica surface per g. of the gel. The adsorption per sq. cm. of the surface is considered to be the same for both the gels at the same equilibrium concentration C_2 .

$$\text{Therefore,} \quad C_u \text{ for A} = C_u \text{ for B or } C_{ua} = C_{ub}$$

$$\text{Hence} \quad S_a/S_b = m_a/m_b = A_a/A_b$$

where A_a and A_b represent the areas per g. of the two gels. Thus by determining the selectivity of the two gels at the same equilibrium concentration, the ratio of the specific areas can be found out. In the following tables the ratio of selectivity of the gels A and B are given.

TABLE V.

C_2 .	Pyridine-heptane.			Alcohol-carbon tetrachloride.			Alcohol-benzene.		
	S for gel A.	S for gel B.	S_a/S_b .	S for gel A.	S for gel B.	S_a/S_b .	S for gel A.	S for gel B.	S_a/S_b .
0.20	0.290	0.264	1.06	0.184	0.176	1.05	0.184	0.176	1.04
0.25	0.281	0.266	1.06	0.168	0.162	1.04	0.170	0.163	1.04
0.30	0.269	0.252	1.07	0.156	0.149	1.04	0.155	0.148	1.03
0.35	0.251	0.237	1.06	0.142	0.135	1.05	0.140	0.135	1.04
0.40	0.230	0.218	1.06	0.129	0.122	1.05	0.127	0.121	1.05

Since the two selectivity curves are almost identical in the case of benzene-heptane mixtures, the ratio of the selectivity is unity at all concentrations.

The ratio S_a/S_b is fairly constant for each binary mixture. It is highest for pyridine-heptane mixtures and is almost identical for the binary mixtures of alcohol with benzene and carbon tetrachloride. It has already been pointed out that the ratio is unity for benzene-heptane mixtures.

SUMMARY.

1. On the basis of the assumption that the liquid held in the capillaries of silica gel, is identical in composition with the bulk liquid, while that adsorbed at the gel surface is responsible for the selectivity noticed, a method of calculating the true adsorption of each constituent has been developed.

2. A method for calculating the excess of the component adsorbed at the surfaces is also presented.

3. Finally the selectivity measurements have been employed in comparing the specific surfaces of two varieties of silica gel.

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